

Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II) and Zinc(II) Complexes with Acetylacetone and Butanone Thiosemicarbazones

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A number of complexes of the type ML_2 , ML_2X_2 or ML'_2X_2 and $NiL(NO_3)_2$, $NiL'(NO_3)_2$, where $M = Co^{II}$, Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} ; L - acetylacetone thiosemicarbazone, L' - butanone thiosemicarbazone; $X = Cl$ or NO_3 , have been synthesised and characterised on the basis of elemental analyses, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, infrared and electronic spectral data.

THIOSEMICARBAZIDE and thiosemicarbazones have aroused special interest due to their activity against viruses, protozoa small pox and certain kinds of tumour¹⁻³. It is a well established fact that drugs increase the activity when administered in the form of metal complexes⁴⁻⁵, and a number of metal chelates have been used as antitumour agents⁶. In the cancer treatment, it has been shown that the active species is not the thiosemicarbazone itself but a metal chelate of thiosemicarbazone⁷⁻⁸. Many have taken interest in studying thiosemicarbazide and thiosemicarbazones as potential ligands⁹⁻¹². This communication reports the complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with thiosemicarbazones of acetylacetone and butanone.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Thiosemicarbazones were prepared by known methods¹³. Ethanol solution of metal salts was refluxed with ethanol solution of thiosemicarbazones in 1 : 2 ratio for 0.5-1.0 h. Volume of the resulting clear solution was reduced to 10 ml by a rotary vacuum evaporator and the solution was left overnight. The resulting crystalline compounds were filtered under suction, washed with ethanol and ether, and dried in vacuum. ML_2 type of complexes were prepared by reacting aqueous solution of the respective metal acetates with ethanol solution of the ligand (L) in 1 : 2 ratio. Metal and sulphur in the complexes were estimated by standard methods. Conductance was measured in 0.001 M acetone solution of the complexes using a Toshniwal conductance bridge. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made at 25° on solid specimens

by Gouy method. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Unicam Sp-1000 and a Beckman IR-12 spectrophotometers. Electronic spectra were studied in 0.01 M methanol solutions of the complexes by a Hilger Watt Uvispeck spectrophotometer. The relevant analytical data are presented in Table 1 and spectral data in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

Complexes reported in the present investigation have the general composition ML_2X_2 or ML'_2X_2 and ML_2 , where M is Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} or Zn^{II} , L is acetylacetone thiosemicarbazone, L' is butanone thiosemicarbazone, and X is Cl or NO_3 , excepting two nickel(II) complexes of the type $NiL(NO_3)_2$ and $NiL'(NO_3)_2$. These are all crystalline compounds. The complexes of cobalt(II) are dark orange or pink, nickel(II) are green or red (nitrate), copper(II) are green, and zinc(II) are white. All the compounds have low molar conductance values in acetone medium indicating their non-electrolytic nature. μ_{eff} values of cobalt(II) complexes are in the range of 4.9-5.1, nickel(II) complexes in the range 3.0-3.2 (excepting the nitrate complexes which are diamagnetic), and of copper(II) complexes are in the range 1.78-1.81 B.M., indicating presumably a spin-free octahedral or distorted octahedral configuration of these compounds.

Infrared spectra of the compounds provide evidence regarding the bonding sites in the complexes. Acetylacetone thiosemicarbazone shows a broad band around 3450 cm^{-1} indicating that there is a free OH group involved in some type of hydrogen bonding, and the ligand is a monothiosemicarbazone. In complexes of the type MLX_2 or

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ML_2X_2 , where L is acetylacetonethiosemicarbazone, ν_{OH} is observed around 3450 cm^{-1} , indicating that the OH group has not taken part in coordination. ν_{C-S} in the ligand is observed at 800 cm^{-1} which is found in the complexes in the $720\text{--}750\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region suggesting the bonding through sulphur of the thiocarbonyl group. ν_{C-N} with some amount of contribution of δ_{NH_2} is found¹³ at 1620 cm^{-1} and a lowering in frequency of this band on complex formation supports the coordination through the terminal hydrazine nitrogen. In the nickel(II)nitrate complexes the position of ν_2 and ν_4 bands of nitrate group occurs at 1280 and 1400 cm^{-1} suggestive of unidentate coordination of the nitrate group. Thus, in complexes of the type MLX_2 and ML_2X_2 , the ligand is bidentate. Similar observation in case of complexes of the type $ML'X_2$ and ML'_2X_2 , where L' is butanone thiosemicarbazone, reveals the bidentate nature of the ligand. In complexes of the type ML_2 , the broad band due to ν_{OH} of the ligand disappears and only sharp bands are seen in $3200\text{--}3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region attributable to ν_{NH} ,

which suggests that the OH group is deprotonated and coordination occurs through oxygen. Lowering of ν_{C-S} and ν_{C-N} bands (Table 2) compared to the ligand suggests the bonding also through the sulphur and nitrogen atoms. Hence, in ML_2 type complexes the ligand behaves as tridentate.

Further, in the far-infrared region, medium intensity bands are observed around $320\text{--}330$ and $280\text{--}300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributable¹⁴ to ν_{M-N} and ν_{M-S} modes, respectively confirming the bonding through the nitrogen and sulphur atoms. In ML_2 type complexes an additional band is found at $440\text{--}460\text{ cm}^{-1}$ presumably due to the M—O stretching mode.

Electronic spectra of cobalt(II) complexes show two bands at $18.0\text{--}19.3$ ($\epsilon=30\text{--}38$) and $8.0\text{--}8.5\text{ kK}$ ($\epsilon=10\text{--}15$) attributable¹⁵ to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (P) and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (F) transitions, respectively suggesting a spin-free octahedral stereochemistry for these complexes. Nickel(II) complexes excepting the nitrate complexes, exhibit three absorption bands at $8.8\text{--}9.8$ ($\epsilon=6$), $13.5\text{--}14.3$ ($\epsilon=7$) and $24.0\text{--}25.6$ ($\epsilon=15\text{--}18$) kK

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	M.p.	Conductance $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
				M	S
CoL_2Cl_2	240	10.5	4.9	11.58 (11.80)	12.62 (12.80)
$CoL_2(NO_3)_2$	205	9.8	4.8	10.41 (10.67)	11.38 (11.57)
NiL_2Cl_2	170	10.2	3.0	11.45 (11.75)	12.40 (12.80)
$NiL(NO_3)_2$	210	11.4	Diamg	15.48 (15.97)	8.51 (8.70)
CuL_2Cl_2	210d	8.8	1.78	12.41 (12.61)	12.48 (12.70)
$CuL_2(NO_3)_2$	250	10.6	1.79	11.22 (11.40)	11.21 (11.48)
ZnL_2Cl_2	218	11.2	—	12.72 (12.91)	12.32 (12.64)
$ZnL_2(NO_3)_2$	235	10.4	—	11.33 (11.69)	11.15 (11.44)
CoL_2	238	8.8	5.0	13.51 (13.81)	14.68 (14.99)
NiL_2	188	9.2	3.2	13.50 (13.76)	14.52 (14.99)
CuL_2	205	9.8	1.80	14.55 (14.72)	14.68 (14.83)
ZnL_2	202	8.5	—	14.85 (15.08)	14.51 (14.77)
CoL'_2Cl_2	204	12.4	5.0	13.65 (13.98)	15.05 (15.26)
$CoL'_2(NO_3)_2$	208	9.6	4.9	12.11 (12.47)	13.21 (13.53)
NiL'_2Cl_2	225	11.5	3.2	13.68 (13.99)	15.02 (15.26)
$NiL'(NO_3)_2$	215d	10.8	Diamg	17.65 (17.91)	9.51 (9.76)
CuL'_2Cl_2	195	8.2	1.81	14.62 (14.97)	14.81 (15.08)
$CuL'_2(NO_3)_2$	175	8.5	1.78	31.01 (13.31)	13.21 (13.40)
ZnL'_2Cl_2	238	10.4	—	15.02 (15.33)	14.68 (15.01)
$ZnL'_2(NO_3)_2$	233	9.5	—	13.48 (13.64)	13.12 (13.35)

d = Decomposed.

TABLE 2—INFRARED (CM⁻¹) AND ELECTRONIC (kK) SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	ν_{C-N}	ν_{O-S}	ν_{M-N}	ν_{M-S}	ν_{M-O}	λ_{max} (e)
CoL ₂ Cl ₂	1595	720	320	290	—	18.0 (30), 8.0 (10)
CoL ₂ (NO ₂) ₂	1598	720	325	285	—	18.5 (35), 8.4 (15)
NiL ₂ Cl ₂	1600	725	325	280	—	8.8 (6), 13.5 (7)
NiL(NO ₂) ₂	1605	730	330	280	—	24.0 (15), 18.0 (35)
CuL ₂ Cl ₂	1593	750	332	285	—	13.8 (35)
CuL ₂ (NO ₂) ₂	1595	745	328	285	—	14.2 (36)
ZnL ₂ Cl ₂	1598	748	325	300	—	—
ZnL ₂ (NO ₂) ₂	1595	745	330	300	—	—
CoL ₂	1600	725	328	295	440	18.5 (36), 8.5 (15)
NiL ₂	1602	725	335	300	445	9.0 (6), 14.3 (7), 2.50 (16)
CuL ₂	1605	730	325	295	450	15.0 (38)
ZnL ₂	1608	730	320	290	460	—
CoL ₂ 'Cl ₂	1595	740	330	285	—	18.8 (36), 8.5 (15)
CoL ₂ '(NO ₂) ₂	1598	745	325	280	—	19.0 (36), 8.4 (14)
NiL ₂ 'Cl ₂	1595	750	328	300	—	9.5 (6), 14.3 (7), 25.6 (18)
NiL ₂ '(NO ₂) ₂	1598	730	330	295	—	18.0 (35)
CuL ₂ 'Cl ₂	1600	725	325	295	—	15.0 (40)
CuL ₂ '(NO ₂) ₂	1605	730	328	290	—	14.5 (35)
ZnL ₂ 'Cl ₂	1595	728	330	300	—	—
ZnL ₂ '(NO ₂) ₂	1593	735	335	295	—	—

regions, assignable¹⁶ to ${}^5A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ (F) \rightarrow ${}^3T_{1g}$ (F) and \rightarrow ${}^3T_{1g}$ (P) transitions, respectively indicating a spin-free octahedral configuration. The nitrate complexes have a broad band around 18.0 kK region showing square planar configuration in conformity with the diamagnetic nature of the compounds. One broad band is observed at 13.8-15.0 kK regions in case of the copper(II) complexes supporting possibly a distorted octahedral configuration. On the basis of elemental analyses, conductance and infrared spectral data zinc complexes have an octahedral environment around the metal ion.

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